

Exploiting Feet Design in Footstep Planning for Quadrupedal Robots

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Abstract—Feet mechanical design and footstep planning play crucial roles in quadrupedal locomotion, particularly in challenging and natural terrains. Despite the emergence of various foot designs for quadruped robots, each possessing unique capabilities such as enhanced grip or terrain-specific adaptability, limited research has been conducted on controllers and planners that exploit these features. Most of the current planning and control strategies rely on the point-foot assumption. This study aims to introduce a methodology for developing footstep planners that are closely integrated with mechanical design, thereby improving grip and performance in rough terrains. A validation of the optimization method using different foot shapes is finally proposed.

Index Terms—Legged Robots, Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of four-legged robots has advanced significantly in recent years due to their potential uses in areas like search and rescue, farming, and environment monitoring. However, one major obstacle preventing widespread use is their inability to traverse rough and dynamic environments (Fig.1). This issue results from the high number of variables involved in contact dynamics on uneven surfaces, leading to slippage and to increased instability of the walking gait. To address this problem, researchers have suggested several methods relying on quick reaction times and adaptability to terrain irregularities to maintain stability. While effective, these approaches carry inherent dangers related to rapid response times and the need for flexibility during balancing manoeuvres. Another strategy involves optimizing the placement of contact points with the ground through careful planning, as well as designing robust feet to provide stable support. Although both topics receive extensive attention, in integrating foot design into the foothold planning process is still an open problem.

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Fig. 1. ANYmal [1] walking on natural and rough terrain.

In this study, we propose filling this gap using a data-driven approach based on neural networks to reduce computational costs.

II. RELATED WORKS

In previous years several foot designs for legged robots have been proposed. The ANYmal robot [1] uses ball-feet and state estimation to detect foot-terrain contact. Humanoid robots like WALKMAN [2], which require a dynamically stable stance, use flat feet that are often actuated. An adaptive foot for bipedal walkers is proposed [3] to increase the compliance with terrain. The same principle is used for quadrupedal robots [4], where embedded compliance is used to grant more grip on the ground. To further increase contact grip, a learning-based footstep planner has been proposed for the adaptive feet [5]. A sensorised flat foot for quadrupedal robots is used in [6] to give terrain information to the locomotion controller. Over uneven terrain, visual sensors are often used to perceive ground irregularities [7]. A classification-based approach has been presented in [8] where visual patterns are used to search for

optimal footholds. In [9] terrain templates are extracted from ground elevation and compared to an expert-demonstration-based model. In [10] the authors used ground features like slope and roughness to plan for low-risk footholds.

Recent advancements in machine learning have enabled researchers to rely on data-driven approaches. Self-supervised learning is used in [11] on a Neural Network (NN) to optimize footholds, and [12] uses a NN to search for energy-efficient footholds.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Foothold optimization

Foothold optimization is an important aspect of quadrupedal locomotion, and it involves selecting the most suitable contact points on the ground for each step taken by the robot. The contact point has to be within a region that allows the robot to walk in the desired direction, with the desired velocity and with a stable stance. This region can be defined as the close proximity to a nominal foothold, computed sampling the trajectory with a nominal stance [14]. Once a nominal foothold is selected, to account for the roughness of the terrain, the foothold selection algorithm performs an optimization step that changes the position in order to guarantee stable contact dynamics.

Overall, the foothold optimization can be expressed by

$$\min C_j + C_f + C_d, \quad (1)$$

This equation is composed of different cost terms. The cost term C_j corresponds to the kinematic feasibility of the candidate foot position, in terms of joint angles. This helps avoid kinematic limits and singularities of the leg. Another term, C_d , is employed to prefer footholds situated within a specific range from the nominal foothold. Keeping the planned steps close to the nominal points ensure that the robot maintains a tracking of the reference velocity, thus C_d act as a tuning parameter between tracking and stance stability. Lastly, the term C_f can be used to include the foot shape in the foothold selection process. Generally speaking, defined a set of features $f^* \in \mathcal{F}$ that describe the optimal contact point for the foot that we are considering, the cost term C_f becomes

$$C_f \propto \|f - f^*\|_{\mathcal{F}}^2, \quad (2)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{F}}$ is a metric in the space of features \mathcal{F} .

B. Learning-based Approach

To parallelize and speed up the cost computation, and in order to evaluate the cost over multiple candidate footholds, we propose a learning-based approach for cost computation. Specifically, we employ a neural network (NN) trained to predict the overall cost value associated with each potential foothold within a given set. To train the NN we utilize data generated through simulations. Given a random terrain elevation map containing various candidate footholds and applying the cost functions, we compute a cost value for each candidate point. This approach keeps the computational cost low and helps deploy the algorithm to real-world applications.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The approach described in this paper could potentially be used to develop a foothold planning algorithm that fully exploits the proprieties of a particular feet design. After testing the NN model, the algorithm could be tested in simulation in a controlled environment to check the feasibility of the selected foothold. Due to the complex nature that feet design could be, real-world experiments are necessary to show that the method is robust to harsh and natural conditions. The NN developed could be deployed easily on non-specialized hardware, and allow for testing on a wide variety of robots.

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